

BorderForce

Flexible system extending automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events

D6.1 – Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan

WP6 - Initial Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization

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Publishable Executive Summary

The D6.1 - Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan is the first deliverable of WP6 “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization” which covers Communication and Disseminations activities of the BorderForce project (GA 101168316), Phase 1 (month 1 - month 15).

The purpose of this deliverable is to outline the strategy and approach for effectively communicating and disseminating the project activities, outcomes, and results to relevant stakeholders. This document serves as a comprehensive guide to ensure that project achievements are widely recognized and leveraged within the context of European border security. The scope encompasses detailed strategies for engaging with stakeholders, setting clear communication objectives, selecting appropriate dissemination and communication tools and establishing KPIs for monitoring effectiveness.

The BorderForce project seeks to strengthen European border security by developing and promoting advanced technologies, creating synergies with other projects and informing policy discussions. The project communication and dissemination objectives are mainly focused on increasing awareness of the project's vision, facilitating collaboration among partners and enhancing the global reputation of European border security technologies.

Key components of the communication strategy include developing a project visual identity, producing digital and print materials, maintaining an active website and social media presence, organizing events to engage with various stakeholders and exploiting the capabilities of social media. The document also emphasizes the importance of targeted dissemination activities, such as participating in specialized events, sharing scientific publications, publishing in specialized press and meeting with policymakers to ensure that the project findings inform relevant policy discussions.

Additionally, the plan outlines KPIs to monitor the success of the communication and dissemination activities, ensuring the project objectives are met and the impact of the activities is measurable.

In conclusion, the Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan is designed to ensure that the BorderForce project reaches its full potential by effectively sharing its results with a wide range of stakeholders, raising awareness of its objectives, and contributing to the advancement of European border security technologies.

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1. INTRODUCTION

BorderForce Communication and Disseminations activities are part of the WP6 “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization” for project’s Phase 1 (month 1 - month 15).

WP6 has 2 deliverables:

1. D6.1 – Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan
2. D6.2 – Initial Communication, Dissemination, Advisory Board Activities and Exploitation/Standardization Plan

GSH is WP leader and responsible for the issue of both deliverables.

1.1. Purpose of the document

The purpose of D6.1 - Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan of the BorderForce project is to outline the strategy and approach for effectively communicating and disseminating the project activities, outcomes, and results to relevant stakeholders.

1.2. Document scope

The D6.1 - Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan for the BorderForce project develops a comprehensive strategy for effectively communicating and disseminating the project activities, outcomes, and results. It includes identifying target audiences, selecting appropriate dissemination and communication channels and establishing KPIs for monitoring effectiveness.

1.3. Partners

The current deliverable has been developed by GSH as WP6 leader with contribution from project coordinator, AIT.

1.4. Definitions, Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Explanation
CA	Consortium Agreement
DG	Directorate General
EU	European Union
Europol	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Q&A	Questions & Answers
R&D	Research & Development
RTDI	Research, Technological Development and Innovation
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise

TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended reality

Table 1. List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

1.5. References

- BorderForce Grant Agreement with No. 101168316
- BorderForce Partners Consortium Agreement

2. DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

The deliverable D6.1 – "Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan," led by GSH, is a public document developed within the framework of BorderForce's WP6. Scheduled for submission in Month 3, this deliverable responds to the obligation set by the EU to communicate and disseminate about project granted under the Horizon Programme.

Therefore, the present document outlines the description and schedule of the planned communication and dissemination activities the communication channels to be utilized for the BorderForce project.

This document consists of the following chapters:

- The Publishable Executive Summary of the deliverable.
- Chapter 1 which includes the Introduction, outlining the purpose, scope, management summary, and relevant definitions, acronyms, and abbreviations. It also introduces the project partners involved.
- Chapter 2 provides the description of the deliverable including presentation of its structure.
- Chapter 3 addresses the overall Communication and Dissemination Strategy, with subsections dedicated to the BorderForce communication and dissemination objectives, target stakeholders, and the general guidelines for disseminating project outcomes.
- Chapter 4 outlines the consortium's role in implementing communication activities.
- Chapter 5 explores the vision behind the project, its alignment with European Border Security objectives, and its visibility through EU funding and Horizon projects.
- Chapter 6 presents the Project Visual Identity, which is key to maintain consistent branding and messaging.
- Chapter 7 elaborates on various Communication tools such as digital and print materials, website management, social media, and videos, among others.
- Chapter 8 discusses Dissemination Activities, focusing on events participation, scientific publications, articles in specialized press, and fostering synergies with similar projects.
- Chapter 9 focuses on monitoring and evaluation, detailing KPIs for assessing the effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities.
- Finally, the document wraps up with a Conclusion, summarizing the strategic approach and the anticipated outcomes of the communication efforts.
- In Appendix indicative lists with events, media and journals are included along with tips concerning social media and a session with Q&A.

3. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY FOR THE BORDERFORCE PROJECT

3.1. BorderForce project

The EU has experienced a surge in fixed border surveillance solutions, including physical barriers, covering 13% of external land borders. The BorderForce project responds to evolving threats by enhancing real-time surveillance capabilities. It introduces a dynamic system, featuring self-sufficient, transportable Command and Control (C2) Stations with configurable and extendable capabilities. These stations incorporate versatile surveillance towers with anti-drone features, integrating data from autonomous monitoring sensors and UAV systems. Dedicated satellite resources, including CubeSat, strategically positioned at high-risk spots, ensure frequent revisits to critical areas. To enable early threat assessment, BorderForce leverages Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT), processing online data for border security threats.

The project emphasizes ethical, legal, and social aspects, safeguarding fundamental rights in border surveillance capability development. BorderForce collaborates with the EU and candidate countries border authorities, customs, and Common Security and Defense Policy (CSDP) entities. It defines scenarios, gathers architecture feedback, and validates end-user feedback. The project emphasizes data exchange, novel user interfaces (e.g., XR), and immersive training for collaborative threat assessment, promoting safety and security while upholding fundamental rights. This solution enhances resource sustainability by improving the coordination and deployment of reusable security measures. The BorderForce solution will be validated in 2 field trials and ensures seamless operations in monitoring the flow of goods, people and information.

By addressing challenges like migration, smuggling, and geopolitical tensions, BorderForce contributes to regional stability, particularly in times of crisis. Overall, it combines technological innovation and international collaboration to bolster border security, prioritizing fundamental rights and ethical considerations.

The BorderForce project can be potentially highly controversial, as it can be mistakenly or malevolently seen as encroaching on fundamental rights and individual liberties. On the one hand, BorderForce develops technologies that aim at reducing the risks and the work-related stress of people securing the EU borders, in accordance with the mandate set forth by agencies such as FRONTEX. On the other hand, border guards deal with illegal migration as well as smuggling of various illegal goods: public communities are often vocally opposed to these things. Great care must thus be taken to tailor our communication.

Therefore, this document emphasizes some critical aspects of the BorderForce project in order to ensure optimal communication outcomes.

3.2. Introduction to Communication and Dissemination

Communication and dissemination, while seemingly similar, differ in their objectives, target audiences and flows of activity.

Communication activities target a broad audience, including the general public and media, with the goal of fostering awareness and generating interest in the project vision. These activities highlight the project value and promote Horizon EU-funded initiatives.

Dissemination, on the other hand, focuses on specialized audiences such as journalists, industry professionals and stakeholders directly related to the project objectives. Its purpose is to share precise information and project results, contributing to the scientific community and ensuring knowledge transfer.

Despite their differences, communication and dissemination must adopt a unified and strategic approach to messaging and content delivery. In today's interconnected world where information flows continuously across traditional, digital, and virtual platforms, a cohesive and consistent narrative is essential to maximize reach and impact.

3.3. BorderForce Communication and Dissemination Objectives

Main objectives for communication and dissemination are defined by the project as follows:

- ◇ Define a clear and distinctive brand identity for BorderForce, consistent online and offline, which represents cornerstone project values
- ◇ Ensure broad visibility of BorderForce work and disseminate its results towards the targeted stakeholder groups so as to effectively promote the BorderForce offering for large uptake
- ◇ Facilitate the exploitation of BorderForce outcomes for the partners and for the overall research communities by promoting the development of innovative solutions for effective socio-economic impact creation
- ◇ Ensure broad visibility and promotion of BorderForce, beyond the programme borders via a strategic and operational coordination of the specific security communities through dedicated efforts embracing all target stakeholders
- ◇ Support the sustainability of BorderForce beyond the project lifetime.

3.4. Introduction to BorderForce Communication and Dissemination

Communication and Dissemination strategy is a blueprint as to how coherently and consistently achieve communication and dissemination objectives set by BorderForce project.

As already mentioned, the purpose of communication is maximising the chances to promote research and scientific results of BorderForce during its lifetime and beyond. A proper dissemination shall ensure that key stakeholders, among which Border and Customs Authorities, can contribute to and act on the findings in a timely way.

Additionally, BorderForce Dissemination and Communication activities except the previous described objectives aim to:

- 1) raise interest and awareness around border protection practices
- 2) encourage European citizens to get informed about Border Control issues

To meet all the objectives previously presented, a coherent and multi-layered strategy needs to be drafted. BorderForce gathers various types of partners (please see next Chapter)– industrial, academic, non-academic and governmental ones – which allows to collect different kind of inputs proper to target different kind of audiences. Throughout all project duration, the whole Consortium and the different Work Packages will be involved in communication activities with these objectives:

- 1) build a community with all relevant stakeholders, ensuring quick uptake and long-term impact
- 2) establish an easily recognisable project identity
- 3) raise awareness of BorderForce on national and international levels.

Based on experience from previous projects, the BorderForce Consortium will use a variety of communication channels (website, social media, participation at conferences) and tools (podcast, leaflets etc.) to disseminate its key message and findings. It will also collaborate with existing stakeholder networks both on national and European levels.

Building a significant and responsive community around the BorderForce project, especially with Border Authorities and Procurement agencies, will facilitate future exploitation plans. The Consortium will bear in mind that its results are to offer a concrete solution to European Border Control challenges and communicate with exploitation stakeholders in that way.

3.5. BorderForce target stakeholders and target audience

One of the most important aspects in effective and successful communication and dissemination strategy is to accurately define the target stakeholders and target audience. Each one of us could be considered as a part of the BorderForce audience today: the instability of the current geopolitical situation has an immediate impact on state economy, citizen’s quality of life and established values of western societies, such as security.

Therefore, several target groups can be identified: citizens, policy makers and media.

As BorderForce is a R&D project, another cluster of audience is all parties with vested interest in research and technology – i.e. private companies, R&D institutions, investors–.

The third cluster of target audience and stakeholders is more institutional: Government departments, EU Agencies, Law Enforcement bodies, Intelligence Agencies, Border Authorities, customs (i.e. Countries, EU member states or neighboring countries to EU, FRONTEX, Europol, DG Home - The Directorate-General of Migration and Home affairs, The Joint Research Center Initiative (DG-JRC) of the European Commission).

A list of BorderForce target groups is described in the following Table.

STAKEHOLDERS	BorderForce VALUE PROPOSITION
Member States/ Ministries and relevant government departments	New framework for the risk management, enhanced border security by leveraging a combination of physical surveillance and digital monitoring, operational flexibility, advanced technology integration such as extended reality and artificial intelligence,

	interoperability with legacy and planned systems and repurposing potential to other domains, such as CSDP missions.
Technology/ service providers, investors, scientific community	Research and development opportunities through the integration of advanced technologies, easy integration of new technical solutions from the use of open standards (where applicable), intellectual property and licensing opportunities, market expansion and diversification since the project results can be used in other domains apart from border surveillance. Credibility and reference ability of results through system trials
Citizens/ travelers, public media	Enhanced security and safety through improved border surveillance and monitoring, economic stability, economic stability due to the increased efficiency of the border surveillance operations, reassurance that surveillance operations are lawful and proportional, ensuring border surveillance solutions keep pace with rapidly evolving risks in an increasingly interconnected world. Open borders (because of enhanced external security) within the Schengen-area allow facilitated border crossings
Regulators and policymakers	Comprehensive analysis of the ethics risks from the use of surveillance technology & of digital tools and new technologies. Understanding of the technologies as a key enabler to meet best practices and assess that legal/ regulatory landscapes remain fit-for-purpose.

Table 2. Target Audiences, BorderForce Grant Agreement

3.6. General guidelines for BorderForce dissemination

1. AIT, the project coordinator of BorderForce, manages the information flow from the project to third parties. It means that the Coordinator should be requested first for any dissemination matter. The official press contact for BorderForce is following:

office_borderforce@list.ait.ac.at

Center for Digital Safety & Security
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Vienna, Austria

2. Project partner GSH, as responsible for WP6 “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardisation”, contributes to the preparation of the content for social media or public dissemination, project website etc.
3. The Security Advisory Board will review the proposed dissemination activity and content and will agree upon its publication
4. Every Partner may present and discuss their specific (technical) work and activities in the context of the project. If a Partners presents the work of others, it must be done only with the explicit permission of the authors of the work. Rules set in the CA (section 8.4) specify following process:
 - give advance notice to the other beneficiaries at least **45 days before the publication**, together with sufficient information concerning the dissemination activity (title, list of authors, abstract of the content and purpose of publication).

- Any other beneficiary may object within **30 days** after receiving notification by sending a written notice to the Coordinator and the Party(ies) involved in the publication. The objection can only be valid if the intended publication significantly harms the legitimate interests of the claiming Party and must include a precise request for necessary modifications, like editing or removing content. The objecting partner can request a publication delay of not more than 60 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 60 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that Confidential information has been removed from the publication as indicated by the objecting partner. If no appropriate steps can be taken to safeguard the legitimate interests of the claiming Party, the dissemination action will not take place.
5. Statements on behalf of the Consortium as a whole must be avoided, unless this has been previously agreed upon by the Consortium and the project coordinator (AIT).
 6. If it is possible, statements of fact must be communicated while statements of opinion must be avoided. If opinions are offered, (e.g. in the case of a social media blog post) it should be clear that this is specific Partner/ person opinion and not representative of the BorderForce project.
 7. Regarding “explicit” permission or approval: “Explicit” refers to a clear, affirmative response from the relevant person or institution. Silence or lack of response does not constitute explicit permission. If no definitive positive reply is received, permission is not granted. Explicit approval from the project coordinator is mandatory for press releases and other written materials. Additionally, “explicit” consent is required when presenting another party’s work or representing the position of another partner.
 8. However, timelines are essential in communication matters. Therefore, the concept of “implicit” permission also applies. “Implicit” permission means that if a deadline for feedback (e.g. comments on the project website) is set and no response is received within that period, permission will be assumed. In summary, for most communication and dissemination activities, except for the project coordinator and explicitly represented parties, implicit permission will be adopted.

4. BORDERFORCE CONSORTIUM

To better serve BorderForce vision and amplify chances of achieving desired results, a Consortium of 16¹ partners from 13 European countries - Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Germany, Greece, Luxembourg, Lithuania, Moldavia, Romania, Slovakia and Spain – was created. All countries have a rich and diverse background in several area of expertise (ethics, scientific, industrial, operational) as well as a deep know-how on border management. They will combine their strengths and develop border security solution based on following technologies and knowledge: Earth Observation, cyber-secure communication, information technology, services development, platform integration, satellite-based systems, software development, artificial intelligence, data fusion, data protection, ethics, risk assessment, sensor technologies.

Given the absolute relevance of the project to the research and business operations of the BorderForce partners, they will endeavor to maximize the impact of their work and deeply exploit the project outcomes for the benefit of all.

Figure 1 BorderForce Consortium partners (crosshatched), dark-blue = EU member states; light-blue = EU candidates; light-green = EU external land-borders, Source: BorderForce Grant Agreement

4.1. Role of the Consortium in BorderForce Communication and Dissemination activities

The Communication and Dissemination strategy cannot work without an active involvement of all BorderForce Partners. Indeed, each of them has access to own networks or contacts that can help maximize the outreach of the project.

¹ the BorderForce Project was initially granted to a Consortium composed of 17 members. Nevertheless, the Austrian Federal Ministry for European and International Affairs (BMEIA) asked for its withdrawal from the project. By the time we are finalizing this Deliverable, an amendment process has been started to officially update this information. Partner BMEIA will therefore not be mentioned in this document.

The contribution of each BorderForce partner is suggested as follows. Nevertheless, partners are encouraged to be part of the Communication and Dissemination activities in more ways if it meets their overall objectives:

Partner Category	Partner	Dissemination Plan
Industrial partner, service provider, SMEs	ED, GSH, SECU EDS, HSE,	Private companies will disseminate via journals and conferences publishing, their own online and social media platforms. Also, an internal dissemination action will be put in place towards internal business units, to enforce and consolidate the knowledge transfer between the R&D and the production.
Border/Custom Authorities, Ministries	GMD, CDB, BMEIA, MBP, MOI, LRM, RBP, SBGS	Stakeholders will disseminate the BorderForce findings in the domain of the organizations' activities and the practitioners' networks, including decision- and policymakers. They will also disseminate the BorderForce concept, methodology and findings in the domain of the organizations' activities.
Leading research and technological development institutions	AIT, VTT, BDI, ECOE	They will disseminate the results in specialized scientific publications and at conferences, as well as in lectures and in training researchers in an early career stage (master students, PhDs, Post-Docs). They will communicate the progress and results beyond the project's own community and show the benefits of research informing general public and society

Table 3 - Individual Dissemination activities, Source: BorderForce Grant Agreement

4.2. Questionnaire

The brilliance of BorderForce consortium is the collective knowledge and plurality that brings into the project deriving from 13 different European countries. Thus, before drafting the Communication and Dissemination Plan, it was decided to involve all partners in the research process and after careful data analysis integrate their input into the strategy design.

4.2.1 Questionnaire structure

After careful consideration regarding the communication and dissemination most essential values, a set of questions was constructed to retrieve the most useful information from the partners. The questionnaire was distributed to the partners present at the Kickoff Meeting with the result of getting back 19 completed questionnaires. Survey was fully anonymous, multiple-choice questions were asked under six different topics (please see questionnaire in Appendix).

4.2.2 Highlights of the data analysis

Reponses provided offer a deeper insight on communication and dissemination variables and qualities that offer a wider stimulus to reflect upon and help construct a more holistic and targeted Communication and Dissemination Plan. Let's examine in more detail two main variables, target audience and communication tools:

- Target audience

Question five provides info on a very important aspect of the communication and dissemination research: BorderForce’s target audiences (see Figure 2). Different choices were given (14) in relation to the project scope and the three top according to responders are: National Law enforcement bodies (14/19), R&D Institutions (13/19) and European Law enforcement bodies (12/19).

Hence it seems that Law enforcement bodies are considered as a critical audience, both on a national level (i.e. National Police, Security Forces) and European level (i.e. FRONTEX, Europol, Euro corps) and should be at the core of the communication and dissemination plan for BorderForce.

Figure 2 Questionnaire – Question 5 BorderForce Consortium Partners responses

- Communication tools

One of the most interesting findings from the data analysis was the unanimous reply to question six and option one. This question was about the means of communication (tools) that partners consider as more suitable for the project. An extensive choice of 19 different tools was provided and the responders could choose up to five ones, being considered not only as the most appropriate for the project but also the most popular in their own country (see Figure 3).

The findings were striking as this was the only question where all responders replied the same: 19 out of 19 chose social media as a tool to prioritize at the communication/ dissemination campaign. This underlines the important role social media play in communication activities regardless of nationality or background, both as a powerful messenger and a mean to shape opinions. Therefore, social media should definitely have a prominent role in the communication and dissemination strategy.

In second place with 9 answers out of 19 are two different tools: Press Release and Stand and Forums Conferences. These are considered traditional ways of communication and dissemination and are a constant part of any communication/dissemination plan.

Finally, another interesting point deriving out of this question is the prioritization of digital news out of traditional ones (online newspapers vs. traditional newspapers). It seems that more emphasis should be given, when drafting the activities, on online outlets rather than traditional ones.

Figure 3 Questionnaire – Question 6 BorderForce Consortium Partners responses

Questionnaire

Which promotional/ad tools are used by your organization? (please select all that apply)

- social media ads
- google ads
- print ad newspaper
- print ad magazine
- radio ad
- online ad banner
- outdoor ad banner
- Other

Which promotional/ad tools are used by your organization? (please select all that apply)

- social media ads
- google ads
- print ad newspaper
- print ad magazine
- radio ad
- online ad banner
- outdoor ad banner
- Other

Which means of communication/promotion do you consider most effective at your country? (please check all that apply)

- social media
- on line news sites
- newspapers print
- national radio
- local radio
- podcast
- National TV
- Euronews
- national newsletter
- local newspaper
- outdoor ad/banner
- Other

which social media do you use at your organisation?

- facebook
- x (twitter)
- youtube
- instagram
- linkedin
- Other

which social media do you use at your organisation?

- facebook
- x (twitter)
- youtube
- instagram
- linkedin
- Other

Will you be willing to repost/reshare post from official social media?

- yes
- no

Will you be willing to repost/reshare post from official social media?

- yes
- no

Which means of communication/promotion do you consider most effective at your country? (please check all that apply)

- social media
- on line news sites
- newspapers print
- national radio
- local radio
- podcast
- National TV
- Euronews
- national newsletter
- local newspaper
- outdoor ad/banner
- Other

Which of the following target audience do you think is important in your country for our project

- Students
- Academics
- Journalists
- Media
- Influencers
- Regulatory Bodies
- Governmental Bodies
- Politicians
- Local Authorities
- Citizens
- Financial Institutions/Funds
- R&D Institutions
- National Law Enforcement Bodies
- European Law Enforcement Bodies
- NGO's
- Other

Which language is mostly spoken in your country (in other please write country official language)

- English
- German
- French
- Other

Please state forums and conferences your organisation will be participating within the next 6 months

5. BORDERFORCE VISION

5.1. Strategic Objectives for European Border Security

It is essential to formulate impactful goals for BorderForce project and Consortium encompassing the concept and idea of Border Security as well as the objectives set by the EU. BorderForce is in a position to participate constructively in the consolidation of the three Border Security pillars, which are:

1. *Minimising the threat of irregular cross-border activities and customs*

Working together with international partners enables the consortium to gain insights into current threats as well as to understand regulations for technology supplying companies, Border & Customs Authorities and citizens. The aim is to explore, compare and report on the improved security together with BorderForce partners.

2. *Showcasing Europe's leadership in security technologies*

BorderForce will improve worldwide available technologies in order to make borders more secure.

3. *Creating a European Border Surveillance Technology with growth potential*

In the line of the BorderForce project, novel technologies will be explored, which will highlight specific areas with needs or opportunities for technology development and research. Such feedback will:

- provide Europe with important directions for RTDI
- anticipate trends
- develop a shared view for the progression of both a secure society and economy.

For these reasons and with these aims in mind, BorderForce vision is:

A flexible system, extending existing automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events to enhance Border Security at the EUs green borders, including coastlines.

BorderForce mission is to reinforce the international dimension of European Border technologies. It helps deepening and materializing security research as well as exploring innovation opportunities.

5.2. Visibility and EU Funding

Communication and Dissemination for Horizon projects

Horizon Europe is the main funding tool for research and innovation aimed, among other goals, at advancing the EU citizens quality of life. It is an obligation set by the EU to communicate and disseminate about the vision, outcomes and technological developments of its granted projects, towards industry innovators, scientific personnel, investors, private companies, policy makers and the civil society (see Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement). Beyond raising the awareness about the project results, the Communication

and Dissemination plan should engage from early stage on the business sector for future possible commercialization.

EU funding should be highlighted throughout the communication and dissemination material – digital or printed – and various activities (events, meetings etc.) undertaken by the Consortium via the constant and clear use of the EU flag (emblem) displayed in a prominent way.

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Also, the following disclaimer should be clear and visible – and where needed, translated to local languages:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

5.3. Project Values

Ethical issues are an essential part of the BorderForce concept, the Consortium is thus called to abide, respect and encourage practices that follow and highlight EU basic values as human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities. The ethical aspect of the project is expected to be enhanced in all communication and dissemination activities throughout the project.

Currently, the EU experiences a combination of unpredictable situations at his Eastern and Mediterranean borders. On the East, there is a ferocious ongoing war, threatening to expand and engage EU member states. In the meantime, the chaos and anarchy caused by the war amplifies various illegal activities from smuggling to trafficking and illegal immigration. Mediterranean EU borders on the other hand, are affected mainly by the conflict in Middle East, as well as the climate change, especially in Africa. Given current state of the world, external security has become a complicated task for the EU. In the meantime, human rights, ethics, quality of life remain unnegotiable values for the Union.

Thus, finding ethical and efficient mechanisms for border management and surveillance in land and sea becomes both a top priority and a challenging task for the EU.

In this context, BorderForce is called to develop innovative technology to ethically address the issue of border management.

Therefore, the BorderForce Communication and Dissemination plan will not only increase the visibility of the project but also raise awareness of the ethical, legal, and social aspects in border surveillance capability development with an emphasis on human rights and EU values.

6. PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

In the era of social media, video and visual are dominant in perception and communication. Brand image attains an even more vital and important role in dissemination while semantics and visual identity constitute the most effective way to convey the strongest message.

Visual brand analysis enables to examine color pallet, logo, typography and general aesthetics in order to asset their impact on brand perception and key messages forwarded to target audiences and stakeholders.

The BorderForce logo is created to convey strength, protection and security, that is why the shield shape has been chosen. In parallel, it needs to convey the humanitarian values of the European Union, thus the colors of the EU were chosen, blue and yellow. The third aspect of the project, technology, is depicted with the small icons withing the shield: satellite, drone, camera, C2 van and grid background.

BorderForce

R=244 G=191 B=59
 HEX f4 bf 3b
 RGB 244 191 59
 CMYK 4 25 89 0
 LAB 81 10 69
 GrayScale 25

R=0 G=51 B=153
 HEX 0 33 99
 RGB 0 51 153
 CMYK 100 91 6 1
 LAB 25 20 -61
 GrayScale 82
 #003399

R=0 G=55 B=255
 HEX 0 37 ff
 RGB 0 55 255
 CMYK 86 73 0 0
 LAB 36 50 -102
 GrayScale 76
 #0037ff

R=255 G=255 B=255
 HEX ff ff ff
 RGB 255 255 255
 CMYK 0 0 0 0
 LAB 100 0 0
 GrayScale 0
 #ffffff

BorderForce

```

R=66 G=66 B=66
HEX 42 42 42
RGB 66 66 66
CMYK 67 60 60 45
LAB 28 0 0
GrayScale 74
#424242

```

```

R=255 G=255 B=255 1
HEX ff ff ff
RGB 255 255 255
CMYK 0 0 0 0
LAB 100 0 0
GrayScale 0
#ffffff

```

```

R=0 G=0 B=0 1
HEX 0 0 0
RGB 0 0 0
CMYK 75 68 67 90
LAB 0 0 0
GrayScale 100
#000000

```



```

R=234 G=234 B=234
HEX ea ea ea
RGB 234 234 234
CMYK 7 5 5 0
LAB 93 0 0
GrayScale 8
#eaeaea

```

```

R=255 G=255 B=255 1
HEX ff ff ff
RGB 255 255 255
CMYK 0 0 0 0
LAB 100 0 0
GrayScale 0
#ffffff

```

BorderForce visual identity is to be used in all external communication and for all promotional material throughout the duration of the project.

7. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Communication activities are defined by project objectives and target audience. Multiple channels and communication assets are chosen not only to maximize the outreach of the project, but also to shape the most relevant message according to audience level and needs.

In the following table the main project communication methods are presented:

Project website	All relevant activities are accompanied with short reports, announcements, photos, news, and links to downloads (e.g., for the project public deliverables and white papers), etc. Beyond the reactive approach following activities, a proactive approach by an overall editorial plan, including the website as well as mailings, to set special articles or series like interviews will help to keep up an interesting up-to-date content during the whole project life.	1 Frequently updated
Social media	Only strictly authorised discussions and exchanges with online communities (e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter)	> 50
Brochure	Electronic and hard copies of the project brochure comprehending a general overview of the project, its challenges and expected impacts in different languages to reach large audiences in different countries, including those where the BorderForce demonstrators will be carried out.	8
Posters	A set of posters will be designed and printed to exhibit at partners' premises and use at events where the project takes presence.	>4
Institutional Presentation	Project Presentation will be created at the beginning of the project, containing basic information about the project (activities, objectives, partnerships, events).	1
Trial videos	A set of videos will be orchestrated, describing the use cases demonstration, their scope and the BorderForce technologies tested and evaluated.	>=4
Info-Graphics	Production of infographics to show the results in a clear and simple way. It is foreseen that during the project implementation phase, 10 infographics presenting various outcomes will be produced.	10
Banner	An attractive large size banner and one stand-up presenting a general image of the project aiming to capture a first interest/attention.	1+1
Final Publishable Report	A Final Publishable Report will be developed to summarise the project's objectives, activities, and achievements. This report will be result-oriented, it will present the tangible results of the project, lessons learnt, and impacts achieved, in order to convince and guide other regions and countries to engage in similar actions.	1

Articles	Tailor-made articles and interviews for publications and other targeted media channels (e.g., EC newsletters, specialised national magazines etc.). Focus will be on AI, technology advancements, security practitioners' methods and demonstration results.	>=5
Newsletter	Periodic newsletters development, publication, and distribution to all the participating partners, conference attendees, website visitors, and other perceived stakeholders / interested parties.	>4, periodical
Press releases	Press releases will be issued to specialised and general media channels at key project milestones (kick-off, major achievements, etc.). A press/media kit will be developed containing detailed press releases, videos (e.g., of project demos), publishable images from the project, few short papers (devoted to some key theme/topic of the project).	>=2
Talks in workshops	Invited talks in workshops and international events of reference as to communicate the project experimentation platform and solutions.	On invite
Innovation Events	Events (as special sessions during the planned hackathons and the large-scale virtual exercise) in Europe with strong stakeholders' representation so that the BorderForce story is spread.	>=1
Marketing Events	Marketing Event, with guided presentation of selected results.	>=1

Table 4. Communication methods, BorderForce Grant Agreement

7.1. Digital and Print material

Various material with informative content will be created in different stages of the project, both in print and digital form such as brochures, posters, infographics, roll up banners. They will be distributed and used either in paper form to events and presentations or in digital form via social media, newsletter and website.

Brochures are expected to provide an overview of the project as well as present highlights and milestones of it.

Infographics are designed to visually convey project details and results in a clear, simple, and accessible way for everyone (in any language).

Posters and roll up banners will be created at different stages of the project according to event targets (i.e. scientific event, industrial congress, workshop with border authorities etc.).

All this material can be translated to local languages, where needed. Online material will be downloadable from the BorderForce website.

7.2. Institutional Presentation

BorderForce presentation is expected to include information about the project basics as envisioned by the consortium at the beginning of the project as main activities, objectives, partnerships, events, as well a more detailed description of projects capabilities and

dynamics. Presentation should be enriched as the project progresses and more material become available, as photos and developments. The Institutional presentation will be translated and adapted to each country language if needed according to communication activities requirements.

7.3. Website www.borderforce-horizon.eu

BorderForce website is designed to be an online hub of information for partners, stakeholders and target audience. It is designed in the colors of the project, blue and yellow while website map and layout keep the strong and agile profile of the BorderForce character.

Main design theme chosen (see Figure 4) aims to convey a scientific project, technologically advanced while providing a feel of interconnection (digital grid created with the lines)

Figure 4 BorderForce website main design theme

Emphasis on the aspect of technology is given by displaying on the home page the four different means used in monitoring: satellites, drones, cameras and C2 Van, so as the visitor can immediately grasp the concept of BorderForce without the need to navigate to any other page of the website.

Figure 5 BorderForce website

The menu of the website is structured as most projects under Horizon, enhancing the Research and Development nature of the project, as to convey trustworthiness and scientific capability. Under tab “Library”, all public deliverables will be provided, while in “Partners” a display of all consortium partners will be available with links to their official websites.

The social media icons are on the upper right-side corner, to provide both a mean of networking and encourage contact but mainly to seek a two-way communication with visitors and hopefully create online communities on social platforms of users interested and invested in BorderForce technology and purpose.

Last but not least, at the bottom of the page, one can find the newsletter subscribe section were visitors by choosing to give their email, give consent to be included in the distribution list of BorderForce news (Figure 6). With time we aspire to build and maintain a distribution list that will grow and will be an important tool in the communication and dissemination activities.

Subscribe to our Newsletter and stay connected

Name *

Email

Figure 6 BorderForce website – Subscribe to Newsletter section

Website creation and structure is implemented in 3 main stages:

1. Creation of the website design, layout and main sections M1-M3
2. Complete the website with actual content, photos, articles, videos, events M3-M15 (contribution of material from all partners)
3. Frequently update the website with milestones, results, events and highlights

7.4. Social Media

Disinformation and fake news make the creation of a project account on multiple online social platforms a necessity. The intention is to have control of the information flow, inform and raise awareness of the BorderForce project. Moreover, social media offer a point of

contact for a two-way communication with target audience and are an excellent source of feedback, exchange of point of views and networking.

Social media chosen for BorderForce project are: LinkedIn, Facebook, X, Instagram and YouTube. Moreover, hashtags are suggested to depict in one word the core purpose of the project while act as a search tool for similar projects or target audience:

Suggested hashtags		
#borderforce	#bordersurveillance	#externalsecurity

Hashtags will be used also on all print material and events info as to further engage on social media attendants and followers.

In addition, a social media calendar is expected to be created as to maintain a constant flow of post and keep high the interest of guests and followers.

Last but not least, as BorderForce is a project of a sensitive nature regarding security aspects, a mechanism of approval is set for updates and information sharing with pre-approved photos and visual material.

BorderForce social media accounts will follow other Horizon and R&D projects with the intent to create a community and exchange reposts and likes to mutually enhance interaction online and achieve greater visibility.

All partners social media professional accounts are expected to interact with BorderForce social media.

Figure 7 BorderForce Social media

BorderForce social media addresses are presented in the following Table.

Social Media	Accounts
X	@borderforce_
Facebook	BorderForce
LinkedIn	BorderForce
Instagram	borderforce_eu
YouTube	borderforce

Table 5. BorderForce social media addresses

7.5. Videos

Videos are an extremely useful tool in communication today. Thus, different videos are expected to be produced on several topics: use cases demonstration, developed BorderForce technologies, general overview of the project.

7.6. Articles

BorderForce articles are expected to be placed on print or electronic media under two basic categories: main results of the project and topical issues (drone technology, artificial intelligence, Earth Observation, border security, technology and ethics etc.) relevant to the project context. Original content is expected to be created and interviews to be led for magazines and websites, newspapers or external newsletters.

Contributions for the production of these articles are expected from all partners involved according to their expertise and involvement in the project.

7.7. Newsletter

A BorderForce digital newsletter will be designed and issued periodically (every six months) to target audience according to GDPR rules. All partners are expected to participate in elaborating the content (photos, text, case studies, milestones) and disseminating to partners own contact lists. Also, a central distribution list will be created and updated throughout the project with emails collected from the website and various events, conferences, workshops, etc. according to GDPR rules.

7.8. Press Release

A press release template will be prepared and distributed to partners to use. A generic distribution list will be created with specialized and general media outlets.

Adaptation into national context and local language will take place where needed. Also, a media distribution list will be created for BorderForce news and updates with journalists covering technology and security topics. Yet, every country could compile its own press list, with journalists from different backgrounds, according to country specificities.

7.9. Final Publishable Report

Part of the Communication plan will be included in the Final Publishable Report containing a summary of the project objectives, activities, and achievements. This report will be a useful tool of reference for other projects and countries wishing to engage into similar projects as BorderForce.

7.10. Events

Under this category, we can find different types of events:

- **Conferences, Exhibitions, Marketing and Innovation Events**

BorderForce is required to attend global and popular public fairs and conferences to maximize visibility but also to establish itself as a modern and updated project.

Also, those events facilitate an opportunity to liaise with journalists, opinion makers and business executives.

- **Forums, Symposium and Workshops**

Forums and Symposiums are excellent places to network and have the chance to present to a large audience the case of BorderForce via a roundtable or panel participation.

Workshops also are an opportunity to present in more detail technical aspects of BorderForce project.

7.11. Podcast

Podcast is a modern and widespread mean of reaching intended audience while establishing a profile as expert on the topic discussed. A series of eight BorderForce podcasts will be designed and release periodically throughout the 30-month duration of the project.

7.12. Additional means of communication

Radio and television channels will be examined for the communication plan as well as opportunities for one-to-one meetings with accredited journalist on technology and security topics.

8. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Industry innovators and technology stakeholders at an international level are in the forefront of BorderForce dissemination activities. The Consortium members will act as a liaison with contacts already developed. Information regarding research, results, specifics and details of the project will be diffused to a more institutional audience and as stakeholders are Ministers and General Secretariats, Heads of research departments and related academia.

While existing networks and acquaintances are at the core of dissemination strategy, it is important to remain open for possible other collaborations and future synergies.

8.1. Participation in Events

The BorderForce Consortium is expected to participate in global industry events, as Forums, Conferences and Fairs, Symposiums, Roundtables, workshops and webinars, with following purposes:

1. Promotion of the BorderForce project via a stand/booth
2. Dissemination and display of digital and print material (brochures, infographics, posters, video)
3. Networking and creation of new relationships with other participants
4. Presentations of BorderForce project
5. Participation in panel discussions.
6. Attracting and engaging specific audiences

Moreover, the BorderForce Consortium could also organize such events or other PR activities and invite specialized audience and stakeholders to participate.

8.2. Scientific publications

The results will be shared through specialized scientific publications and presented at conferences, as well as integrated into lectures and training sessions for early-career researchers (MSc students, PhDs, Post-Docs). Additionally, the project's progress and outcomes will be communicated to audiences beyond the immediate research community, highlighting the benefits of the research to the general public and society.

8.3. Articles to specialized press

Prepare and publish articles at selected press, trade magazines, international journals presenting case studies, knowledge gained, results, and describing the method of achieving objectives of the BorderForce project. Articles are expected to be written by Consortium expert members with deep knowledge of their tasks. Given the sensitive nature of the projects, all articles will need to be approved before getting published.

8.4. Synergies with similar projects

BorderForce is open to create synergies and clusters with similar projects and always available to share information and expertise for the benefit of research and progress.

BorderForce aims to reach out to projects with common interests and create relationships that are mutually beneficial to partners involved. Possible contacts could be:

- [Starlight](#) - Enhancing the EU's strategic autonomy in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) for law enforcement agencies (LEAs) (ends 2026)
- [EURMARS Project](#) – The EURMARS Project aspires to develop an advanced platform to improve the EUROpean Multi Authority BordeR Security efficiency and cooperation. (ends 2025)
- [TENACITy Project - Travelling Intelligence Against Crime and Terrorism](#) (ends 2025)
- [Einstein einstein-horizon.eu](#) (ends 2026)
- [MELCHIOR](#) (ends 2025)
- [Home - FLEXI-Cross](#) (ends 2025)

8.5. Targeted meeting with policy makers

Lobbying is on the agenda for BorderForce partners and everyone is expected to contribute to this aspect. Liaising with policy makers, regulators, government bodies, European agencies would help both inform on BorderForce but also create teams to make compelling presentations to third parties like FRONTEX, Europol, The Directorate-General of Migration and Home affairs (DG HOME).

A Q&A is created to assist all partners in their meetings (see Appendix).

9. MONITORING COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

Communication and Dissemination strategy is expected to be monitored and re-adjusted according to changes in the geopolitical situation.

9.1. Communication KPI's

To effectively monitor the impact and success of communication activities, KPIs will be established to evaluate and measure the outcomes of the planned initiatives. The following Table outlines the relevant KPIs per activity, ensuring continuous assessment and improvement of communication strategies.

Communication method	KPIs
Project web site	1 Frequently updated
Social media	> 50
Brochure	8
Posters	>4
Institutional Presentation	1
Trial videos	>=4
InfoGraphics	10
Banner	1+1
Final Publishable Report	1
Articles	>=5
Newsletter	>4 periodical
Press releases	>=2
Talks in workshops	on invite
Innovation Events	>=1
Marketing Events	>=1

Table 6. BorderForce Communication methods and relevant KPIs, BorderForce Grant Agreement

9.2. Dissemination KPI's

The project aims to engage with the scientific community and key strategic decision-makers, as mentioned above. The BorderForce Consortium is committed to ensure the effectiveness and impact of these engagement activities by establishing and actively monitoring KPIs which will track the reach, quality, and influence of dissemination efforts, ensuring alignment with project objectives and facilitating continuous improvement throughout the project's lifecycle.

Type	KPIs
Exhibition stands in the industry innovation events/fairs	>5
Publication in highly ranked international journals and magazines	>8
Contributions in international peer-reviewed conferences	>8
Cluster with European projects and other initiatives	>5
Targeted Meetings with policy makers	>6

Table 7. BorderForce Communication methods and relevant KPIs, BorderForce Grant Agreement

Each Dissemination activity will be recorded under the following fields, to better keep track of progress:

- Type of Activity
- Title of the Presentation
- Date
- Country/City
- Activity details
- Audience type reached
- Consortium participant

10. CONCLUSION

BorderForce is a highly relevant project that addresses fundamental needs and values at the heart of the EU way of life. Its vision prioritizes people, aiming to enhance the daily lives of civil society by promoting safety and supporting the Border Force Authorities.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan is designed to present BorderForce as an open, transparent, and approachable initiative that serves the interests of individuals and upholds human values. Recognizing the dynamic nature of current events and societal needs, the project will remain adaptable throughout its 30-month duration. Public sentiment, emerging issues, and developments in border surveillance will be closely monitored, allowing for adjustments to the campaign strategy to ensure alignment with evolving circumstances.

11. APPENDIX

11.1 QUESTIONNAIRE CONSORTIUM PARTNERS RESPONSES

BorderForce QUESTIONNAIRE															
Kindly reply to the following questions regarding assets and tools of communication, promotion and dissemination available to your country and company/organization.															
1. Which promotional/ad tools are used by (please select all that apply)															
social media ads	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12	
google ads	<input type="checkbox"/>													1	
print ad newspaper	<input type="checkbox"/>	1				1						1		4	
print ad magazine	<input type="checkbox"/>	1				1					1		1	5	
radio ad	<input type="checkbox"/>	1										1		2	
online ad banner	<input type="checkbox"/>	1			1	1			1				1	7	
outdoor ad banner	<input type="checkbox"/>	1			1	1			1					5	
other	<input type="checkbox"/>										1		1	3	
2. Which social media do you use at your															
facebook	<input type="checkbox"/>		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12	
x (twitter)	<input type="checkbox"/>	1												3	
youtube	<input type="checkbox"/>					1	1	1					1	5	
instagram	<input type="checkbox"/>		1		1	1	1							6	
linkedin	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1	1				1	1	1		1	1	11	
Other	<input type="checkbox"/>											1		3	
3. Which means of communication do you (please check all that apply)															
social media	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	18
on line news sites	<input type="checkbox"/>	1			1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	12
newspapers print	<input type="checkbox"/>					1	1							2	
national radio	<input type="checkbox"/>		1	1	1			1		1	1			7	
local radio	<input type="checkbox"/>									1				3	
podcast	<input type="checkbox"/>									1				2	
national TV	<input type="checkbox"/>		1	1	1	1	1				1			8	
Euronews	<input type="checkbox"/>									1				1	
national newsletter	<input type="checkbox"/>									1	1		1	5	
local newspaper	<input type="checkbox"/>							1	1					2	
outdoor ad/banner	<input type="checkbox"/>						1							1	
other	<input type="checkbox"/>													0	
4. Which language is mostly spoken in (in other please write country official language)															
English	<input type="checkbox"/>					1	1			1	1	1		8	
German	<input type="checkbox"/>								1		1			3	
French	<input type="checkbox"/>														
other	<input type="checkbox"/>														
5. Which of the following target audience do you think is important in your country for our project															
Academics	<input type="checkbox"/>					1	1			1	1		1	9	
R&D Institutions	<input type="checkbox"/>	1			1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	13	
Journalists	<input type="checkbox"/>										1		1	2	
Media	<input type="checkbox"/>			1		1					1		1	5	
Influencers	<input type="checkbox"/>														
Citizens	<input type="checkbox"/>	1								1			1	4	
Politicians	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1					1		1			1	7	
Regulatory Bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>					1	1	1	1					6	
National Law Enforcement Bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	14	
European Law Enforcement Bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	12	
Governmental Bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>					1	1	1	1			1	1	8	
Local Authorities	<input type="checkbox"/>	1		1	1		1	1	1				1	7	
Financial Institutions/Funds	<input type="checkbox"/>											1		2	
NGO's	<input type="checkbox"/>					1	1	1				1		4	
other	<input type="checkbox"/>														
6. Which of the following means of communication/promotion should be prioritized at the projects campaign? (please select up to 5)															
social media	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	19
social media campaign	<input type="checkbox"/>	1								1	1	1	1	6	
online ads	<input type="checkbox"/>			1							1			3	
paid media	<input type="checkbox"/>			1										1	
radio local	<input type="checkbox"/>													1	
radio national	<input type="checkbox"/>													1	
on line newspapers	<input type="checkbox"/>													6	
traditional newspapers local	<input type="checkbox"/>	1								1	1		1	6	
traditional newspapers national	<input type="checkbox"/>									1				1	
Euronews TV station	<input type="checkbox"/>													2	
national TV	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1		1					1	1		1	6	
digital newsletter	<input type="checkbox"/>			1						1		1		4	
scientific papers	<input type="checkbox"/>	1						1	1	1		1		7	
Press Release	<input type="checkbox"/>		1		1	1	1	1				1	1	9	
podcast	<input type="checkbox"/>	1										1		2	
stands at forums/conferences	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1		1				1	1		1	1	9	
workshops	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1		1	1			1			1		7	
PPT presentations/closed meetings	<input type="checkbox"/>	1						1				1		4	
expert panelist	<input type="checkbox"/>	1	1					1	1				1	6	
other	<input type="checkbox"/>														

Thank you

11.2 TABLES WITH EVENTS AND MEDIA/ JOURNALS

Indicative table with List of Events follows (list will be updated).

event	website	date	city
Mobile Deployable Communications	https://www.smgconferences.com/defence/uk/conference/mobile-deployable-communications	28-29 January 2025	London
European Drone Forum 2025	https://eudroneforum.org/	17-18 February 2025	Dusseldorf
World Border Security Congress	https://world-border-congress.com/	25-27 March 2025	Madrid
ICCTHS 2025: 19. International Conference	https://waset.org/counter-terrorism-and-human-security-conference-in-april-2025-in-athens	3-4 April 2025	Athens
Beyond Innovation Expo 2025	https://www.beyond-expo.gr/press-2024-09-05/	4-6 April 2025	Athens
Annual Conference on EU Border	https://www.era.int/cgi-bin/cms?_SID=b41f9d6d4f2f12212eb325f78d10cdbf5d996a6101142907970018&_sprache=en&_bereich=artikel&_aktion=detail&idartikel=133259	10-11 April 2025	Tier & Online
The European Police Congress	https://www.european-police.eu/	20-21 May 2025	Berlin
Border Management & Technology Summit	https://ibmata.glueup.com/event/border-management-technologies-summit-europe-2025-123285/	4-6 June 2025	Talin
Gartner Security and Risk Management	https://www.gartner.com/en/conferences/emea/security-risk-management-uk	22-24 September 2025	London
Berlin Security Conference	https://www.euro-defence.eu/	18-19 November 2025	Berlin
Space Tech Expo	https://www.spacetecheurope.com/register-your-interest-2025	18-20 November 2025	Bremmen

Table 8. Indicative List of Events for BorderForce

Indicative table with List of Media and Journals follows.

Press	website
Border Security Report	https://www.border-security-report.com/
Janes	https://www.janes.com/osint-insights/defence-news
Defense News	https://www.defensenews.com/
AP Border Security	https://apnews.com/hub/border-security
Defense Redefined	https://defencereDEFINED.com.cy/en/
Euronews	https://www.euronews.com/tag/border-controls
European Security and Defense	https://euro-sd.com/
Science Business	https://sciencebusiness.net/
TechCrunch Europe	https://techcrunch.com/
Journals	
ACM Journals	https://dl.acm.org/journal/tist
Taylor and Francis online	https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rjbs20/current
World Customs Journal	https://www.worldcustomsjournal.org/
International Journal of Crime, Justice and Social Democracy	https://www.crimejusticejournal.com/
Journal of Global Security Studies	https://academic.oup.com/jogss

Table 9. Indicative List of Media and Journals for BorderForce

11.3 DISSEMINATION TIPS AND TRICKS

11.3.1 Introduction

With time, the BorderForce project will increase its dissemination activities. Every project partner has resources allocated to Dissemination, and this is an opportunity to show everyone else how great we are- as a project idea, as a team and individually.

The materials we need to effectively promote BorderForce are words and pictures.

This document aims to provide you with tips and tricks to maximise the effect with minimal input.

We are not a PR agency, and we do not want to become one. BorderForce has very cool messages to convey, but there are also risks involved- especially in our initial media exposure where it is important to get the right message across.

BorderForce : Flexible system extending automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events.

11.3.2. 7 text tips for events and visits snippets for Social Media

1. Write to an 15year old (8th Grade)

2. Keep It Short and Simple

All jargon goes away when you write like Hemingway did. There is a free App to help you- it shows your long sentences, unnecessary adverbs, superlative adjectives, and passive phrases. And, with hints for alternatives.

<http://www.hemingwayapp.com/>

3. Write to the reader

Because no one cares about what we do. Readers only care what they can get from what we are doing. So then, write from the readers' perspective. Make them the hero. A list of features? B-o-r-i-n-g. Words that paint a picture for how the reader's life will improve, that's the ticket.

4. Call to Action. A good formula for a social media post starts with a thought-provoking question and an invitation for your followers to take action

Ask a short question or make an impactful statement to pique interest. Don't confuse your fans by asking for too many actions. For example: "Watch our video then come back and comment and share our post."

5. Break Some Punctuation Rules

Unlike email or web text where block capitals are considered rude or aggressive, it's OK on social media! Use block capitals to create excitement.

6. Check Your Spelling and Grammar

Spelling and grammar needs to be good. Poor spelling and grammar reflect badly on our project and will give our audience the impression that we are not on top of our game. If you are targeting and posting in different languages, then be sure to have a native speaker checking the posts before you go live.

7. Use pictures to enhance the words

11.3.3 7 picture tips in taking a good pic for Social Media

As a general rule keep in mind that journalists nowadays if they are in need of photos, usually they search social media to find one. As with text, the same applies to photos, journalists could make use of the on online or print material. Thus whenever you take a photo think if this photo could be on an article and second could it be, does it show something that I dont want to be published?

Don't zoom

Smartphone cameras are improving, but the second you start zooming, you lose picture quality. It sounds simple, but simply get closer! Or, take the photo then crop it later. If you do it this way, your picture won't turn out grainy or blurry.

Framing and Composition

If you've ever taken an art class or have read anything about photography composition, then I'm sure you have seen something about the rule of thirds. Rather than placing your subject directly in the centre of the frame, attempt to shoot your photos with the subject

in the left or right third of the frame. This technique stimulates a viewer to spend more time looking at the photo than if the composition was directly symmetrical.

Use natural light

Smartphones aren't great with lighting, so to compensate for this make sure you take photos near natural light. Going outside is a great option, but if you need to shoot indoors, shoot near a window. However, you don't want to shoot directly into the window or your photo will be too bright. Instead, put your product off to an angle and take the picture with your back to the window.

Use a creative but simple background

When you're snapping a photo, the background matters. Suppose you want to take a picture of a person or technical device. The device is the focal point, but you want to select a nice background too. Select a painted wall to stand in front of or go outside and take the shot with foliage in the background.

Background ideas:

Go outdoors and find a clear, colorful, or bright background like the side of a brick building or find a colored wall to shoot in front of. Use forests, stone, tiles, or rock walls as a background.

Take a variety of shots

Practice makes perfect, and variety helps. If you take two or three shots of the same object/person in a different variation you're bound to get a slew of great pics. Eventually, you'll have a stockpile of shots that you can rely on. With these tips, no one will know that your photos were snapped with your phone.

Effective Editing

There is nothing wrong with filtering for creative purposes, often a filter is a way to add artistic expression. However, there becomes a point at which filtering and using the editing options on mobile apps becomes a little over the top.

To make your images 'pop', without exploding them, try enhancing a few of the following:

- Adjust your photo's shadows and highlights to give it a look true to real life. Since our cameras can only see in stops of light, the shadows and highlights are usually too dark, or overexposed in high contrast lighting (see below).

- Slightly bring up the vibrance, not the saturation, when attempting to make your image more colorful. Over-saturation is a tell-tale sign you over-edited the photo.
- Crop your image to achieve the rule of thirds and straighten the alignment so your horizon lines aren't crooked.

Put A Story Behind the Image

In addition to good photos, tell people what's happening in the photo, or write something interesting! Everyone loves seeing beautiful scenery, but what does it mean to the project? By pairing your images with good writing you'll be able to keep your audience's attention for *longer*, which will help them to remember your project long after they log off.

Hashtags and Sharing

If you're not satisfied with how many people your photos are reaching online, take some time to research different groups and hashtags your photos can be seen through.

11.3.4 10 Tips for Social Media Videos

Find a quiet, private, well-lit place, free from possible interruptions.

1 Keep the camera steady

You wouldn't mail out a thousand brochures with a crooked logo, so why would you make a social video with a shaky hand? Your audience will be able to better focus on the story if the video has a smooth picture quality.

2 MIC

If audio is key to the story, consider an external microphone. Perhaps your video will feature a few witty bits of dialogue or the sounds of animals crooning in the night. Whatever audio effect you're going for, your story will pack more punch if the viewer can clearly hear all the action.

3 Don't use digital zoom

Though it sounds like a good idea in theory, when you use digital zoom, it can make for a very blurry video. Until technologies evolve, avoid the zoom and just move closer to the person or object you're trying to capture.

4 Lighting is key

Smartphone cameras have small image sensors so if you try to shoot in a dark environment, it will give you grainy, low-quality video. Choose a brightly lit setting for your video. Also keep in mind that the auto exposure on mobile phones is often slow to adjust when changing from one scene to the next, so be mindful when moving from dark areas to bright ones. Avoid backlighting and direct overhead spotlighting.

5 Keep it short

A fascinating scientist giving an enlightening Ted Talk might earn hundreds of thousands of YouTube views with a 15 or 20 minute video, but for the most part, shorter is better. Twitter videos are capped at 30 seconds, Instagram has a 60-second maximum and Snapchat videos are capped at 10 seconds. BUT to make a 30 second final Video you will need to shoot about 10 minutes of interviews. DO keep the camera on- and keep the answers short- your interviewee can repeat the answer as many times as it takes!

6 Avoid Q&A

One of the biggest pitfalls of an interview is the question and answer format. People have a natural tendency to answer questions in a certain way. They often lead their answers with uncertainty, saying things like “I guess it would be...” or “I’d have to say...” Some directors will then remind the subject to “answer in complete sentences,” which usually doesn’t change the response, but causes the interviewee to interrupt their own answer with an apology for not using a complete sentence.

Instead, try avoiding questions altogether. Treat the interview as a conversation with questions like, “Tell me about your experience with the current System or, “Describe the conditions here.” You’ll find that when prompted like this interviewees naturally answer in complete sentences, and they’re often more enthusiastic and natural with their responses.

7 Use B-Roll

B-roll, for those unfamiliar with the term, is footage you can cut to while someone speaks. Without b-roll, we’d be stuck watching minute after minute of a person sitting and talking. With b-roll, the speaker’s points can be reinforced with related imagery. B-roll is incredibly important in interview videos. Not only does it keep things interesting, but it gives you the ability to edit the interview without creating jumps. The best b-roll relates to what’s being said. For instance, if someone says “This is a really difficult environment,” you can show video sequences of the area (if possible- otherwise fake it!).

A great rule of thumb is to schedule as much time for getting b-roll footage as you do for getting interviews. During that time, the cameraman should try to capture as much footage as possible, showing anything from people working together to materials lying on a desk.

8 Pause Briefly Before Asking Each Question

Why? Ask your editor. He or she will LOVE you for it. It makes for good clean cuts when you edit your footage. Let’s say your interviewee talked about 3x longer than he needed to to answer your question. You can cut out 2 thirds of what he said, but if his last statement is still trailing off while the audio of your next question overlaps his, it makes it very tough to edit out that 2 thirds later.

9 Avoid Speaking While Your Interviewee is Speaking

Your affirming, “yes,” “uh huh,” “ok,” “Oh, I see,” makes it difficult to edit those points in the interview. Say them once in a while when it’s natural and you’re confident that you’ll be keeping that segment in the video, but other than that, try to stay quiet.

10 Smile Frequently: It Puts Everyone at Ease

Not only does it put your interviewee at ease and help them feel comfortable, but it’s also very inviting for viewers. They probably don’t notice you’re doing it, but your smiles will help them enjoy the interview more and have a more positive feeling about what’s being said.

11.3.5 7 tips for difficult Journalists Questions

1. “Bridging”

Bridging is a technique that gets you from the question asked to the answer you want to give (often a key message). Bridging is a crutch for politicians. The next time you find yourself infuriated with a politician avoiding the question pay close attention to the

language they are using. They're probably bridging with phrases like: "What's important to remember..." "Let's not forget..." "Before I answer that..." "Let me put that in perspective..."

2. Keep your game face on, stay calm and return to your messages.

Look for opportunities to express positivity and pride in the work your organization does.

3. It's Okay to Say "I Don't Know"

No matter how much you prepare, you'll probably not know the answer to every question. If you don't know, say so, and promise to get an answer after the interview. Yes, you want to be helpful to the media, but never guess or speculate.

4. Never (Ever) Repeat a Negative

When you answer a reporter, don't repeat the negative portion of the question in your response. Doing so raises the issue in a listener's mind. Instead, avoid the negative altogether and return the conversation to your messages.

Journalists will sometimes use negative phrases in their questions. Very often the interviewee repeats this negative language, even when they are defending themselves and rebutting the accusation. For example you might be asked: "This is very disappointing isn't it? Aren't you disappointed?" You answer: "I wouldn't say it's disappointing..." But you just have. The journalist's negative language can now be attributed to you. Whether it's broadcast or press, they have a neat soundbite with you using their negative phrase. Don't repeat negative language.

5. Do not Speculate

Journalists are obsessed with the future. Journalism has sometimes been described as the "relentless pursuit of the new". If we don't know something, we can always speculate about it and invite you to do the same. "What would happen if...?" is fascinating to the media but risky for interviewees. Even something as anodyne as "Where do you see turnover in three years' time?" can make you a hostage to fortune. In crisis situations in particular, speculating on the cause of the incident or it's possible consequences is very dangerous. If you don't know, then don't guess.

6. The oft-repeated question

Why do journalists keep asking the same question again and again? You're asked a difficult question and you answer it with the line that you decided to take. The journalist looks quizzical and then asks the same question only in a different form. Or perhaps they go on to ask a couple of other questions and then come back to this question. Then they do it again. Then they apologise or look confused or frustrated – and ask it yet again.

Why won't they leave it alone when you've already answered it? The simple truth is that many people, when asked the same question again and again will (out of boredom, politeness or a mix of both) eventually give a slightly different answer and then the journalist has them.

If the journalist asks you the same question five, six, seven or more times then smile, be polite and give the same answer every time. Better still, try and move the conversation on to something more positive from your point of view.

7. You're Always on The Record

Sometimes a tough question comes after the formal end of an interview. You might think your comments no longer matter. But remember, everything you say is fair game—no matter when you speak. And don't forget this old trick used by some television reporters: After turning off the camera they might keep recording sound, including your post-interview remarks.

11.3.6 FAQ – Answers for critical Questions

The overall message of the project is following: **applied research not only means developing and applying new technologies, but above all building them in a way that makes sense for people and help them work in a safe and reliable way.** Projects such as BorderForce have precisely the aim of investigating these developments while respecting SELP (Social, Ethical, Legal and Privacy) aspects. How can new technologies be meaningfully designed and applied to both comply with individuals' rights and high security standards? These questions are to be answered by a dialogue between different experts across Europe gathered in a project Consortium, among which SELP Partners ensuring the compliance of research with these aspects.

Q: *BorderForce focus is on development of a flexible system, extending automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events. What does this mean, what is BorderForce about?*

A: The BorderForce project responds to evolving threats by enhancing real-time surveillance capabilities. It introduces a dynamic system, featuring self-sufficient, transportable C2 Stations with configurable and extendable capabilities. These stations incorporate versatile surveillance towers with anti-drone features, integrating data from autonomous monitoring sensors and UAV systems. Dedicated satellite resources, including CubeSat, strategically positioned at high-risk spots, ensure frequent revisits of critical areas. To enable early threat assessment, BorderForce leverages OSINT, processing online data for border security threats. The project emphasizes ethical, legal, and social aspects, safeguarding fundamental rights in border surveillance capability development.

BorderForce collaborates with EU and border authorities, customs and CSDP entities from candidate countries. It defines scenarios, gathers architecture feedback, and validates end-user feedback. The project emphasizes data exchange, novel user interfaces (e.g. XR), and immersive training for collaborative threat assessment, promoting safety and security while upholding fundamental rights. This solution enhances resource sustainability by improving the coordination and deployment of reusable security measures. The BorderForce solution will be validated in field trials to become TRL7. It ensures seamless operations in monitoring the flow of goods, people, and information. Addressing challenges like migration, smuggling and geopolitical tensions, BorderForce contributes to regional stability, particularly in time of crisis. Overall, it combines technological innovation and international collaboration to reinforce border security, prioritizing fundamental rights and ethical considerations. BorderForce will make the tasks of Border Guards simpler, faster, more secure and will enable a complete situation threat assessment combined with suggested reaction scenarios.

Q: What's the role of AIT within the project?

A: Today people want to move and travel both freely and safely. Fast and secure access control, seamless border crossing, queue-less passenger checks at the land borders and quick identification of individuals are the key to better security and convenience. Our experts develop systems to monitor land border areas and coast lines for relevant movements using novel technologies such as edge-based sensor platforms. This helps the BorderForce-system to understand if the movements are because of irregular migrations or problematic customs events. AIT develops furthermore a XR based system that helps to deploy and setup the sensors before their operation to achieve the best performance with the selected sensors. Last but not least AIT provides image analytics for publicly available data such as location estimation for images or if they are real or synthetic in order to understand the quality of data for the better use by border authorities.

Over the past decade, AIT has successfully adopted a leading European role in the field of modern IT-based border controls and property protection. In recent years, all major EU initiatives in this context have been led and driven by AIT.

Our goal is to support authorities in their work in the field by providing them with sustainable new technologies that can be well-defined and responsibly deployed.

Q: Which migrants/customs can be stopped by BorderForce?

A: BorderForce is developing new technologies that allow the EU Border Guards and custom authorities to fulfil their duty as efficiently as possible. The technologies we are developing reduce both risks and work-related stress of the people securing EU borders in accordance with the mandate set forth by agencies such as FRONTEX. In line with the European Integrated Border Management concept, the Agency coordinates its cross-border crime related activities also with Europol and other relevant actors.

Our goal to support border guards in the best possible way for enabling a secure European Union without illegal activities and goods circulation. We are researchers and developers. Together with the industry partners involved, we are fostering their competitive advantages and, by that, strengthening the business location Austria.

Q: What is considered during development?

A: From the very beginning, we have paid particular attention to user-friendliness in the system development but also to a responsible interaction with new technologies in order to fulfil the demanding requirements of border guards and customs. Therefore, all actors are involved in the development and design process right from the start.

Q: Where else could these technologies be used in the future?

A: This is not our task. We are developing technologies for a specific and well-defined use case; to solve specific problems. But of course, we will use the new developed methods and tools in future research projects if it makes sense.

Q: Are social, legal and ethical conditions respected? How?

A: Funding programs of the European Union pay particular attention to social acceptance and respect of SELP (Social, Ethical, Legal and Privacy) aspects. All projects funded by the EU are first subject to a strict and transparent evaluation. The selection process is led by

independent experts from an EU Ethics Commission. Each application must take into account ethical aspects in a way that will determine the quality, and therefore the possibility to fund, the proposed research. It can be reached by setting up an Advisory Board with experts in SELP from independent institutions, for example. Each funded project has the obligation to deliver an Ethics report, guaranteeing that these issues have been discussed and integrated in the research. Therefore, a SELP monitoring of the project is ensured from its very beginning.

Q: *What are the current border challenges or mega trends ?*

A : BorderForce is developing a technological solution and approach for border security. We are not involved in politics. Current challenges and mega trends are to be found in the FRONTEX strategic risk report 2024.

BorderForce

Flexible system extending automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events

